

Appendix B. First registered Japanese Spitz dogs per country

This appendix lists the earliest documented registered Japanese Spitz in each country where the breed has been established. Entries are based on official stud book records.

Country	Date of Birth	Dog Name	Origin
Japan	1947.08.06	Hakuryū-go (White Dragon)	—
Norway	1967.03.10.	Sabina of Moon Light	Japan
Sweden	1973.01.21	Daniel of Rose Garden	Japan
Finland	1974.10.25	Alvretens Chinchiro	Sweden
Denmark	1979.06.08	Beo-San / Tu-San	Sweden
United Kingdom	1976.06.27	Alvretens Jicho of Norsken	Sweden
Australia	1979.07.11	Norsken Amida	UK
France	1992.01.03	PIA of the Valley of Seven Castles	Denmark
Italy	1984.11.12	Take-Maru of Yokohama Takada	Japan
Germany	1987.11.26	Zuzushii-San von der Hausruckhöhe	Austria
Austria	1986.03.24	Tu-San Noriko of Nippon	Denmark
Russia	1994.06.20	Odorikko von der Hausruckhöhe	Austria
Slovenia	1991.05.14	Mitshubishi Yuki von der Hausruckhöhe	Austria
Czech Republic	1997.04.01	Kawairashii von der Hausruckhöhe	Austria
Poland	1998.06.09	Rowleys Martini Bianco	Sweden
Poland	1998.06.27	Noidens Just White Magic	Sweden
Estonia	2009.12.05	Agrarium Tatakai of Prashanti	Finland
Latvia	2009.11.11	Houndbrae Akush	UK
Brazil	2002.10.05	Ryuuchi Of Maruko Nomura	Japan
Canada	2017.03.28	Nikita de la Forêt d’Innam.	France
Canada	2017.12.04	Chilly Coco du Ray de Mussy	Switzerland

This table demonstrates the dispersal pattern of the breed from Japan through Sweden (the first non-Japanese country, 1973) to the Nordic countries and United Kingdom, then to Continental Europe, and most recently to the Americas and the Baltic states. The Austrian “von der Hausrückhöhe” kennel served as a secondary dispersal point for Central and Eastern Europe in the 1980s–1990s.